

Assessment of Complications Associated with Beta Thalassemia in Patients from Thi-Qar Governorate: A Descriptive Study

Noor Kadhim Abed ✉

*Department of Medical Physics, College of Applied Medical Sciences,
University of Shatra, Shatra, Iraq*

Abstract

These studies were conducted at the Centre for Genetic Hematology in Thi-Qar governorate during the period of November 2024 until February 2024. This study aims to determine thalassemia through all aspects (age, gender, place of residence) as well as the prevalence of thalassemia and the control group according to ABO. It is also the relationship of thalassemia with patients with spleen hyperplasia and hepectomy. the Study have including (40) patients with thalassemia beta divided between (25 males) and (15 females). Patients are divided into three age groups (14 to 34 years old), the first group ranges from (14 to 20) years, the second group ranges from (21 to 27) years, and the third group between (28 to 34) years, the dominant age group was 20 (40.0%) 12 males and 8 females while the first age group is 15 (30.0%) 8 males and 7 females ,the second age group is 15 (30.0%) 8 males and 7 females. According to the study conducted on sex, there is no significant difference between the sexes, while thalassemia is a genetic disease that is transmitted from parents to offspring. Through the study of the ABO system, these results also showed that there are no significant differences between blood groups within one sex between (males and females). The questionnaire shows that all patients over the age of 20 have undergone spleen removal but with regard to hepatitis, there is no infection for all patients.

Keywords: *Beta thalassemia; Thalassemia complications; Iron overload; Blood transfusion; Thi-Qar Governorate.*

Suggested citation: Abed, N.K. (2026). Assessment of Complications Associated with Beta Thalassemia in Patients from Thi-Qar Governorate: A Descriptive Study. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 3(3), 268-278. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2026.3(3).25

Introduction

Beta thalassemia is an inherited blood disorder caused by mutations in the beta globin gene and impaired beta globin production, ultimately leading to the formation of ineffective red blood cells, chronic anemia, and a host of other clinical consequences that significantly impact disease-related morbidity and mortality rates (Origa, 2017).

Patients with beta-thalassemia experience a reduced life expectancy due to disease complications and the effects of chronic blood transfusions, such as iron overload (Borgna-Pignatti et al., 2004; Taher & Saliba, 2017).

Patients can be classified into three types based on clinical symptoms and genotype: thalassemia major, thalassemia intermedia, and thalassemia minor. The alternative classification of major and intermediate forms of clinically significant beta thalassemia is based on transfusion requirements: transfusion-dependent beta thalassemia (TD) (Galanello & Origa, 2010; Weatherall & Clegg, 2001). Individuals with non-transfusion-dependent beta-thalassemia require regular blood transfusions throughout their lives,

while those with the condition may only require occasional transfusions. Patients with transfusion-dependent beta-thalassemia typically exhibit a phenotype of thalassemia major, characterized by early clinical presentation due to severe anemia requiring lifelong, regular blood transfusions. Improvements in the care of TD B-thalassemia have led to improved quality of life and long-term survival outcomes, but regular transfusions are – still associated with significant risks (Cappellini et al., 2014).

This condition is characterized by a decrease or absence of beta-globin chain synthesis. The resulting relative excess of unlinked alpha-globin chains leads to their deposition in red blood cell precursors in the bone marrow, resulting in their premature death and thus a disruption in the red blood cell formation process (Rund & Rachmilewitz, 2005). The phenotypes of beta-thalassemia vary, ranging from severe thalassemia major requiring blood transfusions to the milder form of thalassemia intermedia. Patients with the primary form of the disease suffer from severe anemia, microcytic hypochromic anemia, and enlargement of the liver and spleen, and typically seek medical attention within the first two years of life. Without treatment, affected children experience severe growth and developmental delays and a reduced life expectancy (Rund & Rachmilewitz, 2005; Cao & Galanello, 2010).

While patients with beta-thalassemia intermedia generally have neural tube defects, regular blood transfusions are used to manage the disease in a minority of adult patients (Taher et al., 2009). However, there is a tendency for symptoms to worsen in a significant proportion of patients. Beta-globin genes are located on chromosome. Both beta-thalassemia and hemoglobin E (Hb E) are genetic globin defects characterized by mutations in the beta-globin gene, leading to changes in the synthesis of the beta-globin chain where this chain is low (B), absent (B), or abnormal (B). In Thailand, both beta thalassemia and hemoglobin E are very common, with prevalence rates ranging from 3-9% and 10-60% respectively (Weatherall, 2001; Nienhuis & Nathan, 2012).¹

Southeast Asia, especially Thailand. Several studies on the efficiency of the immune system in beta-thalassemia have revealed several quantitative and functional defects, including T and B lymphocytes, increased production of immunoglobulins, especially immunoglobulin G (IgG), immunoglobulin M (IgM) and immunoglobulin A (IgA), decreased activity of the complement system with decreased levels of complement 3 (C3) and complement 4 (C4), and increased liver enzymes with increased ferritin (Wanachiwanawin, 2000; Bazi & Miri-Moghaddam, 2016).¹

The present study aimed to assess the spectrum of complications associated with beta-thalassemia among patients in Dhi Qar Governorate through the analysis of clinical and demographic data obtained from treatment center records. Particular emphasis was placed on identifying the most common complications and their associations with patient characteristics, including age, sex, place of residence, ABO blood group distribution, and splenic status (splenomegaly and splenectomy), in order to provide evidence that may contribute to improved disease management and patient care.

Methodology

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the Genetic Hematology Center in Thi-Qar Governorate, Iraq, between November 2023 and February 2024, to evaluate the complications associated with beta-thalassemia and the health problems related to chronic blood transfusion therapy. The study included 50 patients diagnosed with beta-thalassemia who were regularly attending the center for follow-up and treatment. Demographic and clinical data were collected from medical records and direct interviews using a structured questionnaire. Variables assessed included age, sex, place of residence, ABO and Rh blood groups, type of thalassemia (major or intermediate), age at disease onset, parental consanguinity, splenic status (splenomegaly, hepatomegaly, hepatosplenomegaly, or previous splenectomy), and transfusion-related complications. Particular attention was given to the evaluation of viral infections commonly associated with repeated blood transfusions, including hepatitis B virus (HBV),

hepatitis C virus (HCV), and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), based on patients' documented laboratory screening results. The study also investigated the relationship between disease characteristics and the occurrence of complications and transfusion-transmitted infections.

Statistical Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), whereas categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Comparisons between groups were performed using the Chi-square test and independent-samples t-test where appropriate, while associations between variables were assessed using Pearson's correlation coefficient. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Approval

All procedures were conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, and patient confidentiality was maintained throughout the study.

Results

Demographic Characteristic: Age, Sex, and Residency in Thalassemia Patients and Control Group

The current results recorded a significant difference at p. value < 0.05 according to age between patients and control group, was noted the highest proportion patients in the third age group 40%, while the highest proportion of control in the second age group 42.11%.

With regard sex the study noted a non-significant difference at p. value < 0.05 between patients and control group. In contrast, a significant difference at p. value < 0.05 according to residency, was showed the highest patient was situated in countryside 78.0%, and the most control group in city, as in Table 1.

Table 1. Age, Sex, and Residency in Thalassemia Patients and Control Group

Demographic		Patients		p. value
		No.	%	
Age in years	14 - 20	15	30.0	< 0.013 CalX ² =8.64
	21 - 27	15	30.0	
	28 - 34	20	40.0	
Total		50	56.82	
Sex	Male	25	50.0	1.00 CalX ² =0.00
	Female	25	50.0	
Total		50	56.82	
Residency	City	11	22.0	< 0.001 CalX ² =116.7
	Countryside	39	78.0	
Total		50	56.82	

Prevalence of Thalassemia Patients and Control Group According to ABO Groups

This study recorded the most patients' group had O+ 36%, followed by A+ 28%, while the most control group had B+ 36.8%, in addition, non-control group had negative Rh, while 2% of patients had A-, 4% of patients had both B- and O-. the current results also noted a significant difference between groups according to blood group, as in Table 2 and Figure 1.

Table 2. Prevalence of ABO System in Thalassemia Patients and Control Group

	Patients		CalX ² =16.4 TabX ² = 12.59 DF=6 p. value 0.012
	No.	%	
A-	1	2.0	
A+	14	28.0	
B-	2	4.0	
B+	10	20.0	
AB-	0	0.0	
AB+	3	6.0	
O-	2	4.0	
O+	18	36.0	
Total	50	56.82	

Figure 1. Prevalence of ABO System in Thalassemia Patients and Control Group

Descriptive Characteristics and Complication of Thalassemia Patients

The current results recorded a significant difference at p. value < 0.05 according to type of thalassemia disease, was noted the highest proportion patients in with thalassemia major 82%, while the lowest patient with thalassemia intermediate 18%. According to disease complication, the study noted 42% of patients with Splenomegaly, 34% of patients with Hepatosplenomegaly, while only 14% of patients had not disease complication, with significant difference at p. value < 0.05. According to parent consanguinity, the study noted 30% of patients their parent from first and second degree, while only 16% of patients their parent stranger, with non-significant difference at p. value < 0.05. With regard of disease history, the present study showed 72% of patients occurred the disease when they less than year, while only 2% of patients occurred the disease when they more than five years, with significant difference at p. value < 0.05, as show in Table 3.

Table 3. Descriptive Characteristics and Complication of Thalassemia Patients

Patients Characteristics	Thalassemia Type		p. value
	No.	%	
Major	41	82.0	< 0.001 CalX ² =20.4
Intermediate	9	18.0	

Total	50	100	
	Complications		0.003 CalX ² =14.3
Hepatomegaly	5	10.0	
Hepatosplenomegaly	17	34.0	
Splenomegaly	21	42.0	
Non	7	14.0	
Total	50	100	
	Parent consanguinity		0.153 CalX ² =2.64
First degree	15	30.0	
Second degree	15	30.0	
Third degree	12	24.0	
Stranges	8	16.0	
Total	50	100	
	History of the disease		< 0.001 CalX ² =60.5
Less than year	36	72.0	
2 – 3 years	6	12.0	
4 – 5 years	7	14.0	
More than	1	2.0	
Total	50	100	

Descriptive Characteristics and Complication of Thalassemia Patients

The current results recorded a non-significant difference at p. value < 0.05 according to type of thalassemia disease, was noted the highest proportion of viral infection in the patients with thalassemia major 22%, while the lowest patient with thalassemia intermediate 6%. According to disease complication, the study noted 6% of patients with Splenomegaly has viral infection, 12% of patients with Hepatosplenomegaly has viral infection, while only 2% of patients with non-complication had not viral disease, with significant difference at p. value < 0.05. According to parent consanguinity, the study noted 12% of patients their parent from third degree had viral infection, and 8% in patient their parent from second degree, while only 4% of patients their parent in first degree and stranger had viral infection, with significant difference at p. value < 0.05. With regard of disease history, the present study showed the viral infection was increased with increasing the history of viral infection with significant difference at p. value < 0.05, as show in Table 4.

Table 4. Descriptive Characteristics and Complication of Thalassemia Patients

Viral Infection					
Patients Characteristics	Thalassemia Types				p. value
	Positive		Negative		
	No.	%			
Major	11	22.0	30	60.0	0.694
Intermediate	3	6.00	6	12.0	CalX ² = 0.155
Total	14	28	36	72	
	Complications				0.030 CalX ² = 8.95
Hepatomegaly	3	6.00	2	4.00	
Hepatosplenomegaly	6	12.0	11	22.0	
Splenomegaly	4	8.00	17	34.0	
Non	1	2.00	6	12.0	
Total	14	28	36	72	
	Parent consanguinity				0.028 CalX ² = 9.06
First degree	2	4.00	13	26.0	
Second degree	4	8.00	11	22.0	
Third degree	6	12.0	6	12.0	
Stranges	2	4.00	6	12.0	

Total	14	28	36	72	
	History of the disease				< 0.001
Less than year	4	8.00	32	64.0	CalX ² = 37.3
2 – 3 years	4	8.00	2	4.00	
4 – 5 years	5	10.0	2	4.00	
More than	1	2.00	0	0.00	
Total	14	28	36	72	

Discussion

Our age demographic data shows that the average age of the population is between 14 and 20 years, with 30% aged between 21 and 27 years, and 40% aged between 28 and 34 years. This contradicts a study conducted by Asadi-Pooya & Doroudchi, (2004), found the age of 14-20 was 49.6%, from 21-30 years old was 25.2%, and 31-year-old and over was 14.6% ,and this did not agree with our research (Al-Attar & Shekha, 2006).

According to the sex there are no significant differences between gender because thalassemia it is a genetic disease that is transmitted from parents to offspring and to both sex equally. This result is agreed with previous studies obtained (Al-Allawi et al., 2006). A 2007 study by researcher (Abolghasemi et al., 2007) showed that the percentage of men was lower than the percentage of women, and this does not agree with our research.

No statistically significant difference was observed in survival time between the sexes, although the mean survival time for female breast cancer patients was longer than the mean survival time for males (mean survival for females 20.4 vs. 18.0 for males, P=0.11) (Borgna-Pignatti et al., 2005).

Although other studies suggest that male breast cancer cases appear to have a relatively longer survival rate than females (maximum survival of 43 years for males versus 25 years for females), there is no statistically significant difference either. In contrast, in 2005, 344 people were diagnosed with thalassemia, 301 of whom were women (53.3%), representing 46.6% of the total cases. The incidence of thalassemia increases with the rate of consanguineous marriage. All studies conducted on this issue agree that this disease is widespread. Marriage has long been common in both urban and rural areas, especially consanguineous marriage in the early stages, regardless of health considerations (Modell & Darlison, 2008). In rural areas, the primary reason is to preserve inheritance, land, and livestock purely economic reasons. In urban areas, however, it's about maintaining the family's social standing, especially in affluent communities, and preserving lineage. Studies indicate that consanguineous marriage is less common in urban areas than in rural areas, and consequently, its victims are fewer. (ABO system) (Hamamy, 2012; Tadmouri et al., 2009).

The current study showed that the most common blood types among patients are:

In the case of females, the results showed that the most common blood types in the patient group were: O (40%, 26.7%), B (18%, 12.0%), and A (16%, 10.6%). In the case of males, the most common blood types were: The blood types were O 32 (21.3%), B 24 (16.0%), and A 10 (6.70%). These results also showed no statistically significant differences between blood types within the same sex (between males and females) or between the sexes (between males and females). This study is consistent with a previous study (Mondal et al., 2012). This may be due to the lack of correlation between the blood type genotype and the thalassemia genotype. Furthermore, the gene responsible for encoding blood type is located on chromosome 9, while the globin genes are located on chromosomes 11 and 16 (Watkins, 2001).

The study showed that patients had the highest prevalence of blood type A (33.93%), followed by blood type B (29.46%), then blood type O (25.89%), and finally blood type AB (9.82%). In contrast, the highest

prevalence in the control group was O > B > A > AB (Verma, 2013). These results do not match our findings (Verma et al., 2011).

In male and female thalassemia patients, blood type O is the most common, followed by blood type B in males. In females, blood type A is the second most common. Blood type AB is the least common among the ABO blood types in both sexes. In thalassemia patients of both sexes, the highest percentage of Rh antigen is found in blood type O+ (43% in males and 38% in females), followed by blood type B+ (29% in males and 21% in females), while the lowest percentage is found in the ABO blood type. From the current study, it can be summarized that the ABO blood types in thalassemia patients were mostly found in the O+ blood type, and thalassemia was almost never found in the AB- and O- blood types (Marbut et al., 2018; Sinha et al., 2017).

This study is consistent with ours. Concentrated blood transfusion is one of the treatment methods for thalassemia patients, and this process is essential to maintain hemoglobin levels. Blood is transfused to prevent death from anemia in childhood and to allow for normal growth; however, blood transfusions carry some risks, such as viral hepatitis, HIV, iron overload, and splenomegaly (Ali et al., 2021).

The spleen is one of the prevalent and early organs to be affected in children with thalassemia, and the degree of splenomegaly is linked to the severity of thalassemia and compliance with regular blood transfusions (Casale et al., 2014). Splenomegaly and hypersplenism are common complications in children with thalassemia, necessitating splenectomy (Al-Salem & Nasserulla, 2002). In this study, 94 patients underwent splenectomy, 59 males and 35 females. In thalassemia major and thalassemia intermedia, hypersplenism occurs as a result of severe hemolysis. Splenomegaly can be prevented at an early age by initiating regular blood transfusions. However, hypersplenism may develop in children between 5 and 10 years of age. Splenectomy protects patients from morbidity and growth retardation by reducing the need for blood transfusions, improving hemoglobin levels, and minimizing iron overload (Pecorari et al., 2008). Splenectomy is suggested when the need for blood transfusions exceeds 200–220 mL/kg with a hematocrit of 70%, in addition to 250–275 mL/kg with a packed red blood cell count of 60% annually. Meningococcal and pneumococcal vaccination is recommended prior to surgical splenectomy, while post-splenectomy penicillin prophylaxis is suggested to reduce the risk of intractable infections (Ikeda et al., 2005).

The current study included the prevalence of viruses (HCV, HBV, and HIV) in patients with thalassemia who dependent on blood transfusion. The result show the percentage of infection with HCV is 17.33%. The highest rate of infection was in the second and third age group due to the increased the most realistic possibility to exposure to infected blood due to frequent blood hesitation of admission to hospital with increase transfusions or increase contamination device due to intravenous treatment possibility to exposure to or material (Saeed et al., 2014).

Based on previous reports, the prevalence of hepatitis C infection is higher globally compared to healthy blood donors. In Iraq, the percentage of healthy blood donors infected with hepatitis C is less than 1% (Hussein et al., 2017).

However, reports from different geographical areas in Iraq have shown a much higher prevalence of hepatitis C virus antibodies in thalassemia patients, and this finding has been documented in other studies (Abed, 2017). An increased prevalence of hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection was observed among patients with beta-thalassemia, which may be attributed to repeated blood transfusions and the limitations of routine donor screening methods. Since HCV is an RNA virus characterized by high genetic variability and the absence of an effective vaccine, the risk of transmission remains a concern. The use of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) techniques may improve early detection and diagnostic accuracy. In contrast, no cases of hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection were detected in the studied patients, which may reflect the effectiveness of vaccination programs and the greater genetic stability of HBV compared with HCV (Haghpanah et al., 2018; Bazi et al., 2016).

In addition, all thalassemia patients in Iraq receive a specific hepatitis B vaccine before starting blood transfusions. Regarding HIV, the current study shows only one infection in the first age group. This finding contradicts the results of a previous study by Vermeulen et al., (2009), in South Africa and Mirzazadeh (2016) in Iran. When diagnosing viral infections using C-reactive protein (CRP), one of the acute-phase proteins stimulated by interleukin-6 (IL-6) during inflammation in hepatitis C virus, hepatitis B virus, and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infections, a significant increase in the levels of these biomarkers was observed 24–48 hours after infection (Gupta & Pradhan, 2018).

The current study presented the viral infection status according to C-reactive protein. The results showed that the most common type of infection was chronic infection (18 cases, 12.0%), followed by acute infection (8 cases, 5.33%). These results contradict a previous study (Koenig et al., 2003). The increased risk of viral infections is attributed to the frequent blood transfusions received by thalassemia patients, and the likelihood of infection increases with age. The condition has worsened over the past decade (Koenig et al., 2003).

Conclusion

The findings of the present study demonstrated significant variations in age distribution between beta-thalassemia patients and healthy controls, indicating a possible association between age and disease occurrence. In contrast, no significant differences were observed according to sex, reflecting the inherited nature of the disorder, which affects males and females equally. A marked difference was noted in place of residence, with the majority of patients originating from rural areas, whereas most controls were from urban regions, suggesting that geographic and sociodemographic factors may influence disease prevalence. Furthermore, significant differences were identified in ABO blood group distribution, with O+ being the most common blood group among patients and B+ predominating among controls. The study also revealed that most patients developed the disease during the first year of life, while the frequency of newly identified cases declined substantially after five years of age, highlighting the early clinical manifestation of beta-thalassemia and emphasizing the importance of early diagnosis and management.

References

- Abed, R. E. (2017). Investigation of prevalence HCV among thalassemia patients in Thi-Qar province. *University of Thi-Qar Journal of Medicine*, 13(1), 1–8.
- Abolghasemi, H., Amid, A., Zeinali, S., Radfar, M. H., Eshghi, P., Rahiminejad, M. S., Ehsani, M. A., Najmabadi, H., Akbari, M. T., Afrasiabi, A., Malekzadeh, R., & Ghaffari, S. H. (2007). Thalassemia in Iran: Epidemiology, prevention, and management. *Journal of Pediatric Hematology/Oncology*, 29(4), 233–238. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MPH.0b013e3180437e02>
- Al-Allawi, N. A. S., Jubrael, J. M. S., & Hughson, M. (2006). Molecular characterization of beta-thalassemia in the Dohuk region of Iraq. *Hemoglobin*, 30(4), 479–486. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03630260601032891>
- Al-Attar, M. S., & Shekha, M. S. (2006). The prevalence of thalassemia in Erbil Province. *Zanco Journal of Medical Sciences*, 18(2), 46–55.
- Ali, S., Mumtaz, S., Shakir, H. A., Khan, M., Tahir, H. M., Mumtaz, S., Hassan, A., Kazmi, S. A. R., Sadia, H., & Rasool, M. (2021). Current status of beta-thalassemia and its treatment strategies. *Molecular Genetics & Genomic Medicine*, 9(12), e1788. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mgg3.1788>

Al-Salem, A. H., & Nasserulla, Z. (2002). Splenectomy for children with thalassemia. *International Surgery*, 87(4), 269–273.

Asadi-Pooya, A. A., & Doroudchi, M. (2004). Thalassemia major and consanguinity in Shiraz city, Iran. *Turkish Journal of Haematology*, 21(3), 127–130.

Bazi, A., & Miri-Moghaddam, E. (2016). Spectrum of β -thalassemia mutations in Iran: An update. *Iranian Journal of Pediatric Hematology and Oncology*, 6(3), 190–202.

Bazi, A., Miri-Moghaddam, E., & Mashhadi, M. A. (2016). Hepatitis C virus infection in transfusion-dependent thalassemia patients in Iran: A systematic review. *Iranian Journal of Blood and Cancer*, 8(4), 103–110.

Borgna-Pignatti, C., Cappellini, M. D., De Stefano, P., Del Vecchio, G. C., Forni, G. L., Gamberini, M. R., Ghilardi, R., Piga, A., Romeo, M. A., Zhao, H., & Cnaan, A. (2005). Survival and complications in thalassemia. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1054(1), 40–47. <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1345.006>

Borgna-Pignatti, C., Rugolotto, S., De Stefano, P., Zhao, H., Cappellini, M. D., Del Vecchio, G. C., Romeo, M. A., Forni, G. L., Gamberini, M. R., Ghilardi, R., Piga, A., Cnaan, A., & Cogliandro, V. (2004). Survival and complications in patients with thalassemia major treated with transfusion and deferoxamine. *Haematologica*, 89(10), 1187–1193.

Cao, A., & Galanello, R. (2010). Beta-thalassemia. *Genetics in Medicine*, 12(2), 61–76. <https://doi.org/10.1097/GIM.0b013e3181cd68ed>

Cappellini, M. D., Cohen, A., Porter, J., Taher, A., & Viprakasit, V. (2014). *Guidelines for the management of transfusion dependent thalassaemia* (3rd ed.). Thalassaemia International Federation.

Casale, M., Citarella, S., Filosa, A., De Michele, E., Palmieri, F., Ragozzino, A., Amendola, G., & Salvatore, M. (2014). Endocrine function and bone disease during long-term chelation therapy in patients with beta-thalassemia major. *American Journal of Hematology*, 89(12), 1102–1106. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajh.23823>

Galanello, R., & Origa, R. (2010). Beta-thalassemia. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases*, 5, 11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1750-1172-5-11>

Gupta, S., & Pradhan, S. (2018). C-reactive protein: An inflammatory biomarker in viral infections. *Indian Journal of Clinical Biochemistry*, 33(4), 393–400. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12291-017-0683-x>

Haghpanah, S., Davani, M., Samadi, B., Ashrafi, A., & Karimi, M. (2018). Hepatitis C infection in Iranian patients with thalassemia: A systematic review. *Hemoglobin*, 42(3), 162–169. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03630269.2018.1494373>

Hamamy, H. (2012). Consanguineous marriages: Preconception consultation in primary health care settings. *Journal of Community Genetics*, 3(3), 185–192. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12687-011-0072-y>

Hussein, N. R., Haj, S. M., Almizori, L. A., & Taha, A. A. (2017). The prevalence of hepatitis B and C viruses among blood donors attending blood bank in Duhok, Kurdistan Region, Iraq. *International Journal of Infection*, 4(1), e39008. <https://doi.org/10.17795/iji-39008>

Ikeda, M., Sekimoto, M., Takiguchi, S., Kubota, M., Ikenaga, M., Yamamoto, H., Fujiwara, Y., Ohue, M., Imamura, H., Tatsuta, M., Monden, M., & Matsuura, N. (2005). High incidence of thrombosis of the portal venous system after laparoscopic splenectomy. *Annals of Surgery*, 241(2), 208–216. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.sla.0000151794.28346.43>

- Koenig, P., Koshy, M., Dorn, L., Boudreaux, J., & Moore, T. (2003). Hepatitis C virus infection in transfusion-dependent patients with sickle cell disease and thalassemia. *American Journal of Hematology*, 72(1), 29–33. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajh.10243>
- Marbut, S. M. M., Hamdi, M. A., Jumaa, A. M., & Salman, B. A. (2018). Distribution of ABO blood groups in beta thalassemia patients dependent on blood transfusion in Baghdad city. *Journal of Madenat Alelem University College*, 10(2), 1–11.
- Modell, B., & Darlison, M. (2008). Global epidemiology of haemoglobin disorders and derived service indicators. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 86(6), 480–487. <https://doi.org/10.2471/BLT.06.036673>
- Mondal, B., Maiti, S., Biswas, B. K., Ghosh, D., & Paul, S. (2012). Prevalence of hemoglobinopathy, ABO and rhesus blood groups in rural areas of West Bengal, India. *Journal of Research in Medical Sciences*, 17(8), 772–776.
- Nienhuis, A. W., & Nathan, D. G. (2012). Pathophysiology and clinical manifestations of the β -thalassemias. *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Medicine*, 2(12), a011726. <https://doi.org/10.1101/cshperspect.a011726>
- Origa, R. (2017). β -Thalassemia. *Genetics in Medicine*, 19(6), 609–619. <https://doi.org/10.1038/gim.2016.173>
- Pecorari, L., Savelli, A., Guna, C. D., Fracchia, S., & Borgna-Pignatti, C. (2008). The role of splenectomy in thalassemia major: An update. *Acta Paediatrica Mediterranea*, 24, 57–60.
- Rund, D., & Rachmilewitz, E. (2005). β -Thalassemia. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 353(11), 1135–1146. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMra050436>
- Saeed, U., Waheed, Y., & Ashraf, M. (2014). Hepatitis B and hepatitis C viruses: A review of viral hepatitis in Pakistan. *Journal of the Pakistan Medical Association*, 64(5), 563–570.
- Sinha, A., Kumar, S., Kumar, A., Gupta, V., & Singh, P. (2017). Distribution of ABO and Rh blood groups among thalassemia patients. *International Journal of Medical Research Review*, 5(9), 894–898. <https://doi.org/10.17511/ijmrr.2017.i09.10>
- Tadmouri, G. O., Nair, P., Obeid, T., Al Ali, M. T., Al Khaja, N., & Hamamy, H. A. (2009). Consanguinity and reproductive health among Arabs. *Reproductive Health*, 6, 17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1742-4755-6-17>
- Taher, A. T., & Saliba, A. N. (2017). Iron overload in thalassemia: Different organs at different rates. *Hematology*, 2017(1), 265–271. <https://doi.org/10.1182/asheducation-2017.1.265>
- Taher, A. T., Musallam, K. M., & Cappellini, M. D. (2009). Thalassaemia intermedia: An update. *Mediterranean Journal of Hematology and Infectious Diseases*, 1(1), e2009004. <https://doi.org/10.4084/MJHID.2009.004>
- Verma, I. C., Saxena, R., & Kohli, S. (2011). Past, present and future scenario of thalassaemic care and control in India. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 134(4), 507–521.
- Vermeulen, M., Lelie, N., Sykes, W., Crookes, R., Swanevelder, R., Gaggia, L., Jacobs, G., Busch, M., & Murphy, E. (2009). Impact of individual-donation nucleic acid testing on risk of human immunodeficiency virus, hepatitis B virus, and hepatitis C virus transmission by blood transfusion in South Africa. *Transfusion*, 49(6), 1115–1125. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1537-2995.2009.02124.x>
- Wanachiwanawin, W. (2000). Infections in E-beta thalassemia. *Journal of Pediatric Hematology/Oncology*, 22(6), 581–587. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00043426-200011000-00020>

Watkins, W. M. (2001). The ABO blood group system: Historical background. *Transfusion Medicine*, 11(4), 243–265. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-3148.2001.00300.x>

Weatherall, D. J. (2001). Phenotype-genotype relationships in monogenic disease: Lessons from the thalassaemias. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 2(4), 245–255. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35066048>

Weatherall, D. J., & Clegg, J. B. (2001). *The thalassaemia syndromes* (4th ed.). Blackwell Science.

